

A speculative plot of the quantum orbit of the electron, based on the paper "**Electron Geometry**". The paper models the electron as a physical quantum of radius $2.035E-19$ meter, traversing a self-intersecting toroidal orbit.

FIG 1 is a 2D representation of the cross section of a self-intersecting toroidal path. Gamma γ called the major radius, is the radius from the center of the toroidal path to the center of the circle that forms the toroidal path. Beta β called the minor radius, is the radius of the circle that forms the toroidal path.

The self-intersection is greatly exaggerated to illustrate the geometry. The electron self-intersection is very small - it is determined by the square of the fine-structure constant alpha.

The Compton radius **Rc** is one leg of a right triangle and is equal to the square root of $\beta^2 - \gamma^2$. The Compton radius **Rc** is equal to alpha times the Bohr radius **Rb**. As shown in the figure, **Rb** is equal to lengths $\beta + \gamma$.

The electron classical radius is equal to alpha times the Compton radius. It is called the inner radius here to give it a unique subscript **Ri**. As shown in the figure, **Ri** is equal to lengths $\beta - \gamma$. The inner radius is the minimum radius of the self-intersection.

Angle **a** is used to define quantum movement about the circle, in what is called the poloidal direction. This constitutes one speed component of the quantum. Angle **a** will be used in the defining formula for the toroidal path. When forming a toroidal geometry, the circle is rotated about the center of the toroidal path, in what is called the toroidal direction. A second quantum speed component will be defined at the major radius γ .

Done with Maple software:

restart : with(plots) : with(VectorCalculus) : with(Student[Calculus1]) : BasisFormat(false) :

local beta, gamma :

Digits := 24 : interface(displayprecision = 6) :

βe : and γe : are values for minor radius and major radius of the electron orbit in meters, from the paper "Electron Geometry". All unit are in base unit of meters, grams and seconds:

$\beta e := 2.6460270E-11 :$ meter, electron beta, minor toroidal radius
 $\gamma e := 2.6457452E-11 :$ meter, electron gamma, major toroidal radius
 $Rc := 3.8615927E-13 :$ meter, electron Compton radius
 $Rb := \gamma e + \beta e = 5.291772 \cdot 10^{-11}$ meter, Bohr radius
 $\alpha := .0072973526 :$ The fine structure constant alpha
 $h := 6.6260702E-31 :$ Planck's constant in base units m,g,s
 $c := 2.9979245710E+8 :$ Speed of light m/s
 $m := 9.1093837E-28 :$ Electron mass in grams
 $r := 2.035E-19 :$ meter, radius of fundamental quantum

To plot the quantum orbit, we will speculate as to the components of quantum speed. To arrive at speed **Sc** for the fundamental quantum at Compton radius **Rc**, the electron mass is expressed as the equivalent mass of a photon of Compton wavelength $2 \pi Rc$ and energy **hf** where **h** is Planck's constant and **f** is frequency:

$$m = \frac{hf}{c^2} = \frac{h}{c^2} \cdot \frac{Sc}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot Rc} \quad m \text{ is electron mass, } h \text{ is Planck's constant, } f \text{ is frequency}$$

$$Sc := \frac{m \cdot c^2 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot Rc}{h} = 2.997925 \cdot 10^8 \quad \text{equals the speed of light}$$

The speed **Sc** is the speed of light at radius **Rc**, the speed component along the circle of radius **\beta** known as the poloidal direction. At the Compton radius, the speed component in the toroidal direction is zero. We will speculate that the moving quantum exhibits the electron mass at any given radius. For the Bohr radius:

$$Sb = \frac{mc^2 2\pi Rb}{h} = \frac{mc^2 2\pi Rc}{h\alpha} = \frac{Sc}{\alpha} = \frac{c}{\alpha}$$

This shows the quantum speed at the Bohr radius to be about 137.036 times the speed of light. This may seem unlikely, but it may explain why electrons are impervious to most external forces. The quantum speed at the Bohr radius has two components. One is the speed of light **c** along the poloidal direction. The other is the speed along the toroidal direction. We will speculate that they combine as the square root of the sum of the squares to result in **Sb**. The toroidal component then will be the square root of:

$$Sb^2 - c^2 = \frac{c^2}{\alpha^2} - c^2 = \frac{c^2 - \alpha^2 c^2}{\alpha^2} = c^2 \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{\alpha^2}$$

Following is a plot based on these numbers. The quantum radius is not included in the calculations as it isn't noticeable in the plot.

γ is the major radius and β is the minor radius of the self-intersecting toroidal orbit, normalized here to $\beta=1$ for plotting. Speed c is normalized here to $c=1$ for plotting.

$$\beta := 1.0 : \gamma := \frac{\gamma_e}{\beta_e} = 0.999894 \quad \text{gamma scaled for beta equal to 1}$$

$$i := 1.0 : \quad \text{Index i sets beta path speed, poloidal, c normalized to 1.0}$$

$$j := \frac{\sqrt{1.0 - \alpha^2}}{\alpha} \cdot \frac{\gamma}{\gamma + \beta} : \quad \text{Index j sets gamma path speed, toroidal, c normalized to 1.0}$$

Torus formula R:

$$R := (a, b) \rightarrow \langle (\gamma + \beta \cdot \cos(a)) \cos(b), (\gamma + \beta \cdot \cos(a)) \sin(b), \beta \cdot \sin(a) \rangle :$$

Plot definition: For the plot, poloidal angle **a** runs from **0** thru **2π** . The toroidal angle is **b** in the Torus formula. The toroidal angle is angle **a** multiplied by index **j**, the speed ratio determined above.

$$G := \text{spacecurve}(R(i \cdot a, j \cdot a), a = 0 .. 2 \cdot \pi, \text{colorscheme} = ["black", "black"], \text{thickness} = 0, \text{numpoints} = 10000, \text{transparency} = .00, \text{axes} = \text{none}) :$$

$$\text{Tilted view: } \text{display}(G, \text{orientation} = [0, 60, 0])$$

$$Rlen := \|R(a, b)\| : \text{Length of vector R, to check radii, radii normalized to beta equal to one.}$$

$$\text{Inner Radius: } Rlen := \|R(\pi, j \cdot \pi)\| = 0.000106 : \quad \frac{\beta_e - \gamma_e}{\beta_e} = 0.000106 :$$

$$\text{Bohr Radius: } Rlen := \|R(0.0, 0.0)\| = 1.999894 : \quad \frac{\beta_e + \gamma_e}{\beta_e} = 1.999894$$

With an orbiting quantum immersed in a sea of quanta, the model here suggests that electron rest energy is a function of the frequency of collisions of an orbiting quantum with nearby quanta. Collisions must put into motion quanta which make up the electric field. The poloidal path at the center of the electron is largely "vertical". "Vertical" path collisions may put quanta into motion that make up the magnetic field.